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EXAMINING MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR CURBING CONFLICT AMONG HOST COMMUNITIES AND OIL COMPANIES IN NIGER DELTA REGION

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Abstract

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, though richly endowed with petroleum resources, remains one of the most unstable and underdeveloped areas in the country. This study was conducted to ascertain how community-driven development projects can serve as a conflict resolution mechanism between oil companies and their host communities. Anchored on a mixed-methods research design, the study drew data from a structured questionnaire and in-depth interviews within selected communities in the Niger Delta for its analysis. Findings revealed that the sincerity of purpose by oil companies in situating/pursuing community development projects, speedy completion/execution of community development, placing community interest over personal interest by leaders of oil companies' host communities, and equitable allocation of community projects by the oil companies are conflict management strategies. The research concludes that conflict management in the area demands sincerity of purpose by oil companies in situating, pursuing, and speedily executing/completing community development projects, as well as placing community interest over personal interest by leaders of oil companies' host communities and equitable allocation of community projects by the oil companies. Recommendations are offered for policymakers, oil companies, and civil society actors to sustain the conflict management strategies between oil companies and their host communities in the Niger Delta.

Keywords: Management, Strategies, Conflict, Industrial Organisations, Oil Companies, Niger Delta

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Introduction

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, renowned for its vast oil reserves, remains paradoxically mired in poverty, environmental degradation, and social unrest. For decades, the relationship between host communities and oil-producing companies has been characterized by tension, suspicion, and intermittent conflict. These conflicts often stem from grievances related to environmental pollution, inadequate compensation, lack of meaningful community development, and perceived marginalization from resource benefits. As a result, oil operations in the region have frequently been disrupted by protests, sabotage, and militancy, thereby posing significant challenges to national economic stability and regional peace.

In response to these recurrent conflicts, both state and non-state actors, including Oil Companies, have adopted various conflict management strategies. These include Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, community development agreements, stakeholder engagement forums, and the establishment of grievance resolution mechanisms. However, the effectiveness and sustainability of these strategies have come under scrutiny, as hostilities and distrust persist in many communities. There is growing concern that many of these interventions are top-down, poorly implemented, and fail to address the root causes of conflict or reflect the voices of the affected communities.

This study, therefore, seeks to assess the management strategies employed to curb conflict between communities and oil companies in the Niger Delta. It aims to evaluate the design, implementation, and impact of these strategies, identify existing gaps, and explore the extent to which they promote peaceful coexistence and mutual benefit. By shedding light on both the strengths and limitations of current approaches, the study hopes to offer practical recommendations for more inclusive, context-sensitive, and sustainable conflict management in oil-producing areas of Nigeria.

According to the Voices of the Poor study (Narayan and others 2000), based on interviews with 60,000 poor people in 60 countries, Poor People demand a development process driven by their communities. When the poor were asked to indicate what might make the greatest difference in their lives, they responded: (a) organizations of their own so they can negotiate with government, traders, and NGOs; (b) direct assistance through community-driven programs so they can shape their destinies; and (c) local ownership of funds, so they can end corruption. They want NGOs and governments to be accountable to them. Community Driven Development is an effective mechanism for

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poverty reduction, complementing market and state-run activities by achieving immediate and lasting results at the grassroots level (Grootaert, Christiaan, and Deepa Narayan, 2000). Experience has shown that Community Driven Development can enhance sustainability and make poverty reduction efforts more responsive to demand. Community development has also been shown to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of poverty reduction efforts. Because it works at the local level, Community Driven Development has the potential to occur simultaneously in a very large number of communities, thus achieving far-reaching poverty impact. Finally, Grootaert, Christiaan, and Deepa Narayan (2016) stated that well-designed Community Driven Development programmes are inclusive of poor and vulnerable groups, build positive social capital, and give them a greater voice both in their community and with government entities. It is expected that investors, especially from the oil and gas sectors, should contribute their collective efforts to invest in Community Developmental Projects and ensure effective community participation. This will serve as a holistic strategy for conflict management in the area.

In a reactionary manner, Multinational Oil Corporations have responded to the challenges of environmental degradation in the Niger Delta by accepting social responsibilities and demonstrating their commitment to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), by increasing community development spending (Nwosu, 2017). For example, Chevron is reported to have invested \$1.43 million in HIV/AIDS intervention in Nigeria in 2016, engaged in roll back malaria, and river boat clinic projects; spent 7.5 billion naira in the Agbami Scholarship Awards since 2009; and partnered with National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) in business proposals (Chevron, 2017), these are to mention only but a few, with all projects running into either hundreds of millions or billions of naira or millions of US dollars.

Similarly, ExxonMobil affiliate, Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited, operator of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation/Mobil Producing Nigeria Joint Venture, announced their plans (which was considered one of the largest community investments by any company in Nigeria) in the year 2018 to invest up to N13 billion (US\$43 million) in three projects comprising of community health, economic empowerment and education projects in Akwa Ibom State over 18 months (Vanguard ng, May 9, 2018). The three projects comprised a technical skills centre in Ikot Akata, a trauma centre at the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, and an engineering complex at the University of Uyo (Vanguard ng, May 9, 2018).

With all these acclaimed heavy spending and projects, the loggerheads between oil companies and their host communities have continued unabated. This dilemma has

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attracted the attention of several authors. For instance, Eze (2009) in a study entitled “Sociological Approach to Militancy in the Niger-Delta: A study of Warri in Delta state” examined the incessant militancy in the Niger-Delta in a bid to offer a sociological inquiry into the conflicts in the region. Agba, Ikoh, and Ushie (2013) in a study entitled “Developing the Niger-Delta Region of Nigeria through Community Development Committees (CDCs): A Critical Assessment” and Uche, Okoye and Uche (2014) in a study entitled “Sustainable Community Development: An insight into the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) Community Development Projects in Abia State” both examined community development projects in the Niger-Delta region and its attendant impact on the people of the region. While Otega, Danni and BadariahHj (2015) in a study entitled “Nigerian Niger Delta Community Participation: Catalyst for Sustainable Human Development” and Nwosu (2017) in a study entitled “Corporate Social Responsibility of Exxon-Mobil in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria and Community-Industry Relations: A Sociological Jurisprudence Prism” examined the pros and cons of corporate social responsibility and its attendant impact on the people of the Niger-Delta region. However, none of the afore-mentioned studies focused distinctly on Community development projects as a conflict management strategy among Oil Companies in the Niger-Delta. Thus, the idea of this study was conceived.

In the empirical study by Nwosu (2017) on individual and composite factors in corporate social responsibility of ExxonMobil, four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was 1,700 secondary school students, and a sample size of 360 was used for the study. The design of the study was an *expos facto* research design. A four-point Likert scale instrument was used to collect data from the respondents. The results of the statistical analysis of all the hypotheses of his study revealed that the individual and composite factors in Corporate Social Responsibility of ExxonMobil actually significantly affect, relate to, and indeed predict community-industry relations to the extent that the more the company engages in Corporate Social Responsibility under the first five sub-independent variables of participatory development intervention, social investment in healthcare, local community economic empowerment, social investment in education, and development of physical infrastructure, the more the likelihood of a more cordial relationship with the various communities in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The implication is that better community-industry relations are more likely to result when the company engages in or shows more commitment to the established Corporate Social Responsibility.

Although several studies, Uche, Okoye and Uche (2014), Otega, Danni and BadariahHj (2015), and Nwosu (2017) have all examined various aspects of

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developmental problems or shortcomings in the Niger-Delta, which ranged from poor leadership, poor project sustainability, and risk of capture to abuse of community development objectives. These existing research works have not specifically considered a study of Community Development Projects as a conflict management strategy among Oil Companies in the Niger-Delta. The purpose of this study was therefore to fill this research gap by providing empirical data to evaluate strategies of Community Development Projects as an approach for conflict management in the Niger Delta region.

Objective of the Study

This study seeks to examine management strategies for curbing conflicts between communities and oil companies in the Niger Delta region.

Research Question

The question formulated to guide this study was:

What are the management strategies of conflict in host communities of oil companies in the Niger Delta region?

Research Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The reason for this research design is that it focuses on collecting data from a large population at the same point in time using a sample population (Babbie, 2010). The research was conducted in selected host communities within **Akwa Ibom and Delta** states, where ExxonMobil's and Chevron's operations are concentrated. These communities are representative of the broader conflict dynamics in the Niger Delta region and have a history of direct interactions—positive and negative—with the oil company. The researcher believed that members of these communities were in a better position to supply dependable information to examine community development projects as a conflict management strategy among oil companies in the Niger Delta. Thus, following the 2006 population census, *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) has a population of 58,974 (NPC, 2006), while *Ibeno* has a population of 38,539 (NPC, 2006).

Following the 3.5% standardised population growth estimate per annum, the population estimate of *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) by 2020 was 3.5% of 58,974, which is 0.035×58974 , which is 2064. Because a 14-year projection (2006 to 2020) was made,

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2064 was multiplied by 14 to get the projected population growth (2064×14) = 28896. To get the actual population in the year 2020 as projected from 2006, the projected population growth figure (28,896) was added to the *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) population figure of 2006 (58,974). Thus, the population estimate of *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) in 2020 is $28,896 + 58,974 = 87,870$. In line with this population projection estimate formula, the population of *Ibena*, Ibena local government area, by 2020 is 3.5% of 38,539, which is $0.035 \times 38,539$, which is 1,349, and because a 14-year projection (2006 to 2020) was made, 1,349 was multiplied by 14 ($1,349 \times 14$) to get the projected population growth of 18,886. To get the actual population in the year 2020 as projected from the year 2006, the projected population growth figure (18,886) was added to the population figure of 2006 (38,539). Thus, the population estimate of *Ibena*, Ibena Local Government Area, in 2020 was $57,425$ ($18,886 + 38,539$). Therefore, the target population for this study was 145,295, which is the 2020 projected adult population of *Otunana* (Warri South LGA) and *Ibena*, Ibena local government area, put together. The sample size of this study was 1,059 respondents. Ten respondents out of the sample size were selected purposively for an In-Depth Interview (IDI).

This study adopted a systematic random sampling method. Thus, following the natural clusters of layouts in *Otunana* and *Ibena* and their housing units. Respondents were picked at intervals of 5 housing units. At the end, 529 respondents will be selected from *Otunana*, and 530 respondents will be selected from *Ibena*. The essence of this variation was to ensure that the sample size of 1,059 was met for the quantitative part of the study. A questionnaire and an In-depth Interview (IDI) guide were adopted as instruments for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions. The second instrument (IDI) was used to complement the questionnaire. The purpose was to employ a qualitative method, which is known for exploring grey areas that are not made explicit in the questionnaire.

The researcher employed the services of three research assistants from the study area, who assisted in administering and retrieving the questionnaire on completion by the respondents during the fieldwork. Out of 1,059 copies of the questionnaire administered, 860 copies were retrieved, giving a retrieval rate of 81 percent.

The data collected were properly checked to ensure all items in each of the questionnaires were responded to. Thereafter, responses were coded and analysed using appropriate statistical methods. Frequency distribution tables, percentages, and charts were used to organise and present the quantitative data, while information obtained through qualitative data was thematically analysed, complementing the quantitative

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data appropriately. The study adhered to ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and anonymity and confidentiality were assured.

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of respondents on the measures to foster more cordial relationship between host communities and oil companies

Measures	Frequency	Percentages
Sincerity of purpose by oil companies in situating and pursuit of community development projects	218	37.5
Speedy completion/execution of community development projects by oil companies	120	20.6
Placing community interest over personal interest by leaders of the oil company's host communities	114	19.6
Equitable allocation of community projects by the oil companies	130	22.3
Total	582	100.0

Source: Author's fieldwork

Responses from Table 1 revealed the suggestions on what could be done to help foster a more cordial relationship between host communities and oil companies. Most of the respondents had similar responses grouped into four categories according to their order of magnitude. The table indicates that 37.5% of the respondents suggested sincerity of purpose by oil companies in situating and pursuing community development projects, 20.6% of the respondents noted speedy completion/execution of community development projects by oil companies, 19.6% of the respondents stated placing community interest over personal interest by leaders of oil company's host communities, while 22.3% of the respondents suggested equitable allocation of

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community projects by the oil companies.

Discussion

To manage conflict and foster a cordial relationship between host communities and oil companies in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, most of the respondents had similar responses on sincerity of purpose by oil companies in situating and pursuing community development projects, followed by speedy completion/execution of community development projects by oil companies, placing community interest over personal interest by leaders of oil company's host communities, and finally equitable allocation of community projects by the oil companies. The findings could be attributed to the fact that the respondents had personal experience of the conflict situations as members of the communities.

The findings support that of Nwosu (2017), that the individual and composite factors in the corporate social responsibility of ExxonMobil significantly affect, relate to, and indeed predict community-industry relations to the extent that the more the company engages in corporate social responsibility under the first five sub-independent variables of participatory development intervention, social investment in healthcare, local community economic empowerment, social investment in education, and development of physical infrastructure, the greater the likelihood of a more cordial relationship with the various communities in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The implication is that better community-industry relations are more likely to result when the company engages in or shows more commitment to the established Corporate Social Responsibility.

The findings align with the assertion of Grootaert, Christiaan, and Deepa Narayan (2016) that well-designed Community Driven Development programmes are inclusive of poor and vulnerable groups, build positive social capital, and give them a greater voice both in their community and with government entities. It is expected that investors, especially from the oil and gas sector, should contribute their collective effort to invest in community development projects and ensure effective community participation. This will serve as a holistic strategy for conflict management in the area.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion of this research, the following recommendations are made:

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Oil companies should commit to corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives that add tangible value to the operating environment and address critical development gaps. They should promote good neighbourliness and foster mutual co-existence with host communities. Unscrupulous business practices and environmental degradation must be avoided, while consultative processes and popular participation should be embraced in supporting community development.

Furthermore, oil companies should contribute to building institutions that support human development in oil-producing communities, provide mentoring for the acquisition of productive skills, and award scholarships to aid the development of critical industrial competences. Employment opportunities must also be created for the youth, as research indicates that unemployment is a key factor in youth restiveness, which fuels communal conflicts and violence. Implementing these measures would, in both the short and long term, help to prevent the recurrence of the acrimonies experienced in the past.

Oil companies should also conduct regular studies to identify the specific needs and attitudes of their host communities towards CSR programmes and assess their effectiveness as a conflict management tool.

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